

A complex of taxa around *Purpuricenus wachanrui* Levrat, 1858 (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)

M.L. Danilevsky¹, K. Hodek²

¹A.N. Severtsov Institute of Ecology and Evolution, Russian Academy of Sciences
Leninsky prospect, 33, Moscow 119071 Russia
e-mail: danilevsky@cerambycidae.net

²Havlenova 29, Brno - Štýřice CZ-63900 Czech Republic
e-mail: hkarlos@seznam.cz

Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Cerambycini, taxonomy, new rank, Iran, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Pakistan, Syria, Iraq, Cyprus.

Abstract: New rank is established for: *Purpuricenus wachanrui robusticollis* Pic, 1905, **stat. nov.** New synonyms are proposed: *P. wachanrui* Levrat, 1858 = *P. nanus* Semenov, 1907, **syn. nov.**; *P. w. robusticollis* Pic, 1905 = *P. persicus* Vartanis, 2023, **syn. nov.** *P. zarudnianus* Semenov, 1903 is confirmed as a species.

Introduction

Purpuricenus wachanrui Levrat, 1858 is extremely variable in many known populations (especially in Iran): body bigger or smaller, antennae can be longer or shorter, with 11 or 12 segments in one population, thoracic spines distinct or obliterated, black design of pronotum and elytra can be strongly developed or rather reduced. Similar populations are distributed mosaically in the country and similar forms can be strongly distant that makes difficult subspecies delimitation. Strong individual variability caused several taxa descriptions based on small series of specimens. We are going to show variability level in several populations.

Results

***Purpuricenus wachanrui* Levrat, 1858**

Purpuricenus wachanrui Levrat, 1858: 261 - "Turquie"; Pic, 1905: 391 - région caucasique, Elbourz: Haute vallée de Chahroun; Aurivillius, 1912: 464 (= *haussknechti* Witte = *aleppensis* Witte = *bilunatus* Schaufuß = *schönfeldti* Heyden) - "Türkei, Kleinasien, Syrien, Persien", "Cypern"; Plavilstshikov,

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

- 1940, part. (including *haussknechti* Gahan, 1906): 559, 570, 760 - Asia Minor, Cyprus, Syria, Mesopotamia, Kurdistan, Iran; Villiers, 1967: 363 - Asie Mineure, Irak, Arménie, Iran: “Shemiran, 10 km au nord de Téhéran”, “environs d’Ispahan”, “Shemshak”, “Mardabat”, “Shahrud”; 1979: 115 - Iran: “Ouest du col de Zagheb, près du Khorramabad”, “Daran”, “Taleqan”; Adeli, 1972 - Iran; Lobanov et al., 1982: 253 - Caucasus, Western and South-West Asia; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 214 - Nergram in Nakhichevan Republic of ASSR; Western Asia, Northern Iran; Al-Ali & Ismail, 1987 - 540, part. - Iraq; Rejzek & Hoskovec, 1999: 265 - Turkey; Rejzek, Sama & Alziar, 2001: 266 - Turkey; Rejzek, Sama, Alziar & Sadlo, 2003: 165 - Iran; Sama et al., 2008: 117 - Iran, “Northern and western provinces”; Özdikmen, 2014: 622 - Turkey; 2023: 207, 209 - Turkey: Adana (Misis), Adıyaman (Nemrut Mt., Karadut), Bingöl (Central), Bitlis (Güroymak), Çankırı (between Şabanözü-Orta), Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Konya, Malatya, Muş (Buğlan pass), Tunceli (Munzur Valley, Pülümür), Van (Çatak); Danilevsky, 2020b: 283 - Azerbaijan, Iran, Iraq, Turkey, Cyprus, Syria; Kasatkin, 2021: 298 (= *mesopotamicus* Al-Ali & Ismail) - Iraq, Mosul prov., Siakh-Gyuivez; Turkey (Bulgan Gec., Bitlis, Tunceli), Iran.
- Purpuricenus wachanrui*, Schaum, 1862: 101 (misprint, unavailable name).
- Purpuricenus bilunatus* Schaufuß, 1871: 210 - Insel Cypern.
- Purpuricenus haussknechti* Witte, 1872: 207 - Kurdistan.
- Purpuricenus haussknechti* var. *aleppensis* Witte, 1872:208 - aus der Umgegend von Aleppo.
- Purpuricenus* (s. str.) *wachanrui*, Ganglbauer, 1882: 741 (= *haussknechti* Witte) - “Türkei, Kleinasien, Persien”; Heyden et al., 1891: 346; 1906: 517; Winkler, 1929: 1183; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 199 - Azerbaijan, Iran, Iraq; Danilevsky, 2012a: 149 - Cyprus, Syria, Turkey.
- Purpuricenus nanus* Semenov, 1907: 254, **syn. nov.** - “Hab. Persiam occidentalem: prov. Gilan: pr. pag. Molla-ali”.
- Purpuricenus wachanrui* var. *schönfeldti* Heyden, 1890a: 79 - Sultanabad in Persien.
- Purpuricenus robusticollis* Pic, 1905: 9 - “Perse”; Ambrus & Grosser, 2013: 468 - “Esfahan prov., 40 km SE Aligudarz, Nowghan env.”, “Lorestan, 17 km SW Dorud, Tut village env., 1995 m.”, “Lorestan prov., Tootmashour, 33.41N 48.90E, 1995 m.”; Vartanis, 2023: 1805 - Iran.
- Purpuricenus schonfeldti* var. *atricolor* Pic, 1912a: 4 - “Luristan”.
- Purpuricenus schonfeldti* var. *quadrinotatus* Pic, 1912b: 35 - Perse: Luristan.
- Purpuricenus schonfeldti* var. *diversipennis* Pic, 1915e: 6 - Aleppo.
- Purpuricenus schauffelei* Pic, 1956: 3 - Iran.
- Purpuricenus wachanni*, Davatchi et al., 1959: 241 (misprint, unavailable name) - Iran.
- Purpuricenus mesopotamicus* Al-Ali & Ismail, 1987 - 540, 541, part. - Iraq (Rawanduz): Khan Azad.
- Purpuricenus ivachanrui*, Modarres, 1997 (misprint, unavailable name) - Iran.
- Purpuricenus* (s. str.) *mesopotamicus*, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 199, part. - Iran.
- Purpuricenus* (s. str.) *robusticollis*, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 199, part., Iraq.
- Purpuricenus persicus* Vartanis, 2023: 1803, **syn. nov.** - Iran.

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

Type locality. Asian Turkey without more precise definition.

Description. Head black; antennae 11- or 12-segmented; male antennae from hardly surpassing elytral middle to about 2 times longer than body; female antennae reaching elytral middle; pronotum from red to black, usually red with black anterior and posterior margins, or black with red spots; elytra black with red central spots, which can be very small, widely separated, or larger, touching at middle, or large, widely conjugated, or totally disappeared; males from 10.1 to 19.8 mm long, females from 12 to 16.5 mm long.

Distribution. South-east Turkey, eastwards from Konya to Iranian border; Cyprus; Syria, Aleppo; West Iran from Turkish border to central provinces; Azerbaijan, southern border of Nakhichevan Republic.

The variability of the species is rather different in different populations. Several populations can be adequately represented by displaying significant series of specimens from the corresponding localities.

***Purpuricenus wachanrui wachanrui* Levrat, 1858**

Tabs 1-8

Purpuricenus wachanrui Levrat, 1858: 261 - "Turquie".

Type locality. Asian Turkey without more precise definition.

Description. Red color dominates on prothorax and elytra; body length in males: 10.1-19.5 mm, body length in females: 12-20 mm.

Known populations:

TURKEY

Nemrut Dagi, 45 km NEE Adiyaman, 37°57'51.94"N, 38°44'37.52"E, 14.6.-17.6.2008, R.Ambrus: 28 males and 23 females (R.Ambrus collection) - **Map: loc. 2; Tab. 1;** male antennae 12-segmented with well-developed 12th segment, considerably longer than body (surpassing elytral apices by 5 segments) or hardly reaching elytral apex; female antennae 11-segmented, usually surpassing elytral middle; prothorax red, usually with narrow black anterior and posterior stripes; very rare black with central red spot or totally black; red elytral design as wide transverse band more or less narrowed at middle, often divided by black suture or totally separated in two portions.

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

Buğlan Geçidi, 8 km SE Solhan, 1700-1800 m, R. Ambrus leg. - 4 males, 3 females (R. Ambrus collection) - **Tab. 2(1)** - male antennae 12-segmented with well-developed 12th segment, considerably longer than body (surpassing elytral apices by 5 segments); female antenna also 11-segmented, reaching to about elytral middle; prothorax red with black margins; elytra red with big red areas narrowly separated at middle, touching or widely conjugated.

Buğlan Geçidi, 30 km E Bingol, 14.6.1977, S. Kadlec leg. - **Map: loc. 6**; one pair of big specimens (male - 18 mm, female - 19 mm) - M.L. Danilevsky collection; male antennae 12-segmented with well-developed 12th segment, considerably longer than body (surpassing elytral apices by 5 segments); female antennae also 12-segmented, but with strongly reduced 12th segment, reaching to about elytral middle; prothorax red with black lateral (male) or ventral (female) sides; red elytral design as wide transverse band more or less narrowed laterally.

Hakkâri prov., 3 km N of Hakkâri, R. Ambrus leg. (**Map: loc. 7**); 1 male, 3 females - **Tab. 2(2)** - R. Ambrus collection; male antennae 12-segmented, surpassing elytra by 4 segments; female antennae 11-segmented, reaching elytral middle; prothorax red with black margins; elytra with large red areas widely conjugated at middle (with wide red belt narrowed at middle).

IRAN

Ardabil, 5 km S Deez, 37°16'N, 48°44'E, 1350m, 5.6.2017, K. Hodek leg. (**Map: loc. 9**) - 16 males (body length: 11.3-17.5 mm) and 3 females (body length: 12.1-16.5 mm) - **Tab. 2(3)** - K. Hodek collection; small specimens of this population are very similar to the type specimens of *P. nanus*, but antennae a little longer and always 12-segmented in males and in females, 12th segments in small specimens are considerably reduced, especially in females; antennal length in males is rather variable; antennae of the biggest male are about two times longer than body, but usually in middle size males and in small males - about 1.5 times longer than body, but sometimes - about as long as body; female antennae reaching to about elytral middle; lateral thoracic tubercles indistinct; pronotum red, often with narrow anterior and posterior black stripes or totally red; elytra with central red belt, more or less wide, sometimes narrowed at middle; anterior black elytral area can be very narrow or totally disappeared.

Tab. 1. *P. w. wachanrui* (R.Ambrus collection, photo by R. Ambrus): 1 - 28 males, 23 females, Turkey, Nemrut Dagi, 45 km NEE Adiyaman, 37°57'51.94"N, 38°44'37.52"E, 14.6.-17.6.2008, R.Ambrus leg.; 2 - 1 male, 1 female, Adiyaman environs, R. Ambrus leg.

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

Tab. 2. *P. w. wachanrui*: 1 - 4 males, 3 females, Turkey, Buğlan Geçidi, 8 km SE Solhan, 1700-1800 m, R.Ambrus leg. - R. Ambrus collection, photo by R. Ambrus; 2 - 1 male, 3 females, Turkey, Hakkâri prov., 3 km N of Hakkâri, R. Ambrus leg. - R.Ambrus collection, photo by R.Ambrus; 3 - 16 males, 3 females, Iran, Ardabil, 5 km S Deez, 37°16'N, 48°44'E, 1350 m, 5.6.2017, K. Hodek leg. - K.Hodek collection, photo by K.Hodek.

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

Type series of *P. nanus* Semenov, 1907 (Gilan, Molla Ali River, 36°36'40"N, 49°32'33"E, 370 m, 15.5.1904, N. Zarudnyi leg. **Map: loc. 10**) originally consisted of 5 specimens (1 male and 4 females); body length: 7.4-11 mm. One pair available now; male - **Tab. 3(1)** - lectotype (present designation), with 2 labels - **Tab. 3(3)**: 1 [partly in Russian] - "Гилян: Молла-агы / 15.V.04. / Зарудный"; 2 - "Purpuricenusa / nanus Sem." / "Cotyp." / "A. Semenov-Tian-Shansky det." - collection of Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Saint Petersburg); female - **Tab. 3(2)** - paralectotype (present designation), with 2 labels - **Tab. 3(4)**: 1 [partly in Russian] - "Гилян: Молла-агы / 15.V.04. / Зарудный"; 2 - "coll. Semenov-Tian-Shansky" - collection of Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Saint Petersburg).

Male antennae 11-segmented, shorter than body, reaching last elytral fifth, female antennae slightly surpassing elytral middle; lateral thoracic tubercles obliterated; pronotum about totally red (with narrow basal and apical black stripes); red central elytral band strongly narrowed medially, anterior and posterior black elytral areas rather wide.

Kermanshahan, Shamshir env., 34°59'15"N, 46°25'37"E, 1850 m, 6.6.2015, K. Hodek leg. (**Map: loc. 21**) - 5 males (body length: 14-16.2 mm), 5 females (body length: 14-16.9 mm) - **Tab. 4(1)** - K. Hodek collection; male antennae from about 2 to 1.5 times longer than body, female antennae reaching elytral middle; male antennae 12-segmented, female antennae 11-segmented; pronotum usually red, but one male has black pronotum with two red spots, and two males with wide red areas in the middle of black pronotum; red elytral design usually consists of big triangular spots touching at middle, widely conjugated or contrary narrowly separated; anterior black elytral area always very wide.

Esfahan, "p. Chaharmahal, Ghahderijan 20km W, 23.5.2017, 32°36'N, 51°7'E, 2145m, K.Hodek leg." (**Map: loc. 21**) - 13 males (body length: 7-13.1 mm), 8 females (body length: 10-15.1 mm) - **Tab. 4(2)** - K. Hodek collection; "Isfahan prov., Azizabad, 32°36'N, 51°7'E, 1890 m, 11.6.2018, K.Hodek leg." (**Map: loc. 21**) - 2 males (body length: 8.8-13.0 mm) and 2 females (body length: 11.5-12.0 mm) - M.L. Danilevsky collection; all are also similar to the type series of *P. nanus*; antennae of the biggest male 12-segmented,

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

considerably longer than body (surpassing elytral apices by 4 segments); antennae in smaller males 11-12-segmented; more or less longer than body, or about equal to elytral length, or even shorter; female antennae 11-segmented a little surpassing elytral middle; pronotum red with narrow anterior and posterior black stripes; elytra with wide red central band more or less narrowed medially and wide black apical area; anterior black elytral area can be very narrow.

Esfahan, 20 km southwards Shahreza, 31°48'20.6"N, 51°48'50.9"E, 24.5.2017, Dembický leg. (**Map: loc. 25**) - 3 males, body length: 11.2-13.7 mm and 3 females, body length: 11-12.9 mm - **Tab. 5(1)** - K. Hodek collection.

8 males, 8 females - same locality, J. Dalihod leg. - **Tab. 5(2)** - R. Ambrus collection.

Dark specimens; male antennae 12-segmented with well-developed 12th segment, from rather shorter than body, to little longer than body or surpassing elytral apices by 2-3 segments; female antennae 11-segmented reaching elytral middle; pronotum from totally red to totally black; elytra from black with small red spots, to big red spots separated or conjugated and to wide red belt - transitional population.

North Hamadan, Gardaneh-ye Avadzh, 35°33'N, 49°10'E, 2500 m, C. Naumann leg. (**Map: loc. 15**) - 7 big specimens (M.L. Danilevsky collection): 5 males (body length: 12-16 mm) and 2 females (body length: 14-15 mm); male antennae 12-segmented with well-developed 12th segment, considerably longer than body (surpassing elytral apices by 3-4 segments); female antennae 11-segmented or 12-segmented, but then 12th segment is strongly reduced; prothorax usually with small lateral tubercles; pronotum mostly red with black margins and black posterocentral stroke; sometimes pronotum nearly black with two small central spots; red elytral belt usually interrupted medially, but sometimes complete and wide.

Qazwin, Alamut, 36°26'41"N, 50°35'10"E, 2400 m, D. Murastyi leg. (**Map: loc. 12**) - 2 big males (M.L. Danilevsky collection); antennae 12-segmented with well-developed 12th segment, considerably longer than body (surpassing elytral apices by 4 segments); prothorax with obliterated lateral tubercles; pronotum red with black margins; red elytral design wide, but interrupted medially by black suture.

Tab. 3. *P. w. wachanrui*: 1 - male-lectotype of *P. nanus* Semenov, 1907, Iran, Gilan, Molla Ali River, 36°36'40"N, 49°32'33"B, 370 m, 15.5.1904, N. Zarudnyi leg.; 2 - female-paralectotype of *P. nanus* Semenov, 1907, Iran, Gilan, Molla Ali River, 36°36'40"N, 49°32'33"B, 370 m, 15.5.1904, N. Zarudnyi leg.; 3 - labels of the lectotype of *P. nanus* Semenov, 1907; 4 - labels of the paralectotype of *P. nanus* Semenov, 1907.

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

Tab. 4. *P. w. wachanrui*: 1 - 5 males, 5 females, Iran, Kermanshahan, Shamshir env., 34°59'15"N, 46°25'37"E, 1850 m, 6.6.2015, K. Hodek leg. - K. Hodek collection, photo by K. Hodek; 2 - 13 males, 8 females, Iran, Esfahan, "p. Chaharmahal, Ghahderijan 20 km W, 23.5.2017, 32°36'N, 51°7'E, 2145 m, K.Hodek leg." - K. Hodek collection, photo by K. Hodek.

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

Qazvin, 4 km W Kouhin, 36°22'N, 49°37'E, 1500 m, 31.5.2015, K. Hodek leg. (**Map: loc. 11**) - 1 female (K. Hodek collection); red prothorax, wide central band.

Kordestan, 3.5 km E Dizli, 35°22'N, 46°11'E, 1350 m, 25.5.2019, K. Hodek leg. (**Map: loc. 19**) - 1 male (K. Hodek collection), red prothorax, wide central band, antennae as long as body.

Kordestan, Divandareh, Saral, 35°43'46"N 46°52'53"E, 5-6.2016, Fardin Faizi leg. (**Map: loc. 18**) - 1 male: body length: 13.5mm, 1 female: body length: 10.3 mm (M.L. Danilevsky collection) - male antennae 12-segmented a little longer than body surpassing elytral apices by one apical segment; female antennae 11-segmented reaching to about elytral middle; prothorax with obliterated lateral tubercles; pronotum red with black margins; red elytral dark with two small triangular spots separated medially.

Kordestan, 5 km N of Kamyaran, 2.6.2010, 34°53'N, 46°58'E, 2100 m, Z. Košťál leg. - 16 males, 12 females (Z. Košťál collection), male antennae 12-segmented, from very long, surpassing elytral apex by 4 segments, to rather short, a little longer than body, surpassing elytral apices by one apical segment; female antennae 11-segmented reaching to about elytral middle; no specimens with black thorax or black elytra available.

IRAQ

Penjvin, 35°38'N, 45°56'E, 1300 m, 9.6.1976, J. Macek leg. (**Map: loc. 26**) - 1 male: body length: 14.8 mm; antennae 12-segmented with well-developed 12th segment, considerably longer than body (surpassing elytral apices by 4 segments); prothorax with obliterated lateral tubercles; red with black margins; red elytral design interrupted medially;

Same locality, 11.6.1976 & 20.6.1976, J. Macek leg. - 2 females (M.A. Lazarev collection).

Material (M.L. Danilevsky collection). *Purpuricenus wachanrui wachanrui*: 1 male, Turkey, 30 km E Bingol, 1400m, 14.6.1977, D. Bernhauer; 1 male, 1 female, Turkey, Buğlan Geçidi, NW Mus, P. Bialooki leg.; 1 male, Iraq, Kurdistan, Penjwin, 1300m, J. Macek leg.; 5 males, 2 females, Iran, Hamadan, Gardaneh-ye Avadzh, 35°33'N, 49°10'E, 2500 m, 6.7.1997, C. Naumann leg.; 2 males, Iran, Qazvin, Alamut Mts., 2400 m, 24-25.6.2016, D. Murastyi leg.;

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

2 males, Iran, Davandareh, Saral, 22.5.2016, 1.6.2016, Fardin Faizi leg.; 5 males, 1 female, Iran, Gilan, 5km S Dees, 37°16'N, 48°44'E, 1350 m, 5.6.2017, K. Hodek leg.; 2 males, 2 females, Iran, Isfahan, Azizabad, 32°36'N, 51°7'E, 11.6.2018, K. Hodek leg.

***Purpuricenus wachanrui robusticollis* Pic, 1905, stat. nov.**

Tabs 5(3-4) - 7

Purpuricenus robusticollis Pic, 1905: 9 - "Perse".

Type locality. Iran ("Perse"); most probably - Zagros Mountains.

Description. Black color often dominates on prothorax and elytra; body length in males: 13.8-18 mm, body length in females: 12.9-18 mm.

Known populations:

South Hamadan, Baharab, 34°38'N, 48°10'E, 1600 m, 26.5.2017, K. Hodek leg. (**Map: loc. 29**), 10 males, body length: 9.5-13.2 mm, 4 females: 10-14.9 mm - **Tab. 5(3)** - (K. Hodek collection) - dark specimens dominate; male antennae 12-segmented with well-developed 12th segment, considerably longer than body, surpassing elytral apices by 3-4 segments, or a little longer than body, surpassing elytral apices by 2-3 segments, female antennae 11-segmented, reaching elytral middle; prothorax without lateral tubercles; pronotum usually totally black, but sometimes with wide or narrow red spot, which can be divided in two small portions; elytra usually with two triangular smaller or larger red spots, or totally black.

South Hamadan, Baharab, 34°38'10"N, 48°11'7"E, 1600 m, 20.5.2017, K. Hodek leg. - 3 males, body length: 10.6-11.3 mm and 2 females, body length: 10.8-11.4 mm - M.L. Danilevsky collection.

Esfahan, 40km SE Aligudarz, Nowghan env. 2254 m, 1.6.2009, 33°11'35.11'N, 50°04'46.74'E, 1.6.2009, R. Ambrus leg. (**Map: loc. 34**), 18 males, 22 females (**Tab. 6**) - R. Ambrus collection; very dark specimens dominate; male antennae 12-segmented with well-developed 12th segment from, rather long (surpassing elytral apices by 4 segments) to rather short (hardly reaching elytral apices); female antennae 11-segmented, reaching elytral middle; all males with totally black pronotum; pronotum mostly red in 6 females; 15 males and 4 females with totally black

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

elytra; elytra in other males black with small red spots; elytra with big red areas (often conjugated) in 12 females.

Same locality, 31.5.-1.6.2009, 11°35.11'N, 50°04'46.74'E, W. Grosser leg. - 2 black males, body length: 13.7 mm and 13.3 mm (M.L. Danilevsky collection) - antennae 12-segmented with well-developed 12th segment, a little longer (surpassing elytral apices by 1 segment) or a little shorter than body; prothorax totally black with obliterated lateral tubercles; elytra totally black.

Same locality, 1.6.2009, W. Grosser leg. - 2 males (body length: 16.0-17.8 mm), 6 females (body length: 10.0-16.9 mm), W. Grosser collection; 2 males totally black, antennae 12-segmented, surpassing elytra by 2-3 segments; female antennae 11-segmented, about reaching elytral middle; 2 females - black with small elytral red spots; 2 females - totally black, 1 female black with small elytral red spots, 1 female with pronotal red area and triangular elytral red spots, 1 female black with triangular elytral red spots.

Lorestan, Razan (18 km NWW Dorud), 1800m, 33°33'N, 48°53'E, 26.5.2017, K. Hodek leg. (**Map: loc. 33**); 5 males (body length: 12.9-16.1 mm), 6 females (body length: 13.4-16.5 mm) - **Tab. 5(4)** (K. Hodek collection) - dark specimens; male antennae 12-segmented with well-developed 12th segment, rather long surpassing elytral apices by 4 segments; female antennae 11-segmented, reaching elytral middle; prothorax usually black, or with wider or smaller central red spot; elytra from totally black, to black with small red spots, to big red spots separated or conjugated and to wide red belt; males darker, than females.

Lorestan between Dorud and Kuh-e-Ostoran mt. 2600-3200 m, 4.-6.6.2000, 33°22'N, 49°12'E, M. Kalabza leg.; 7 males, 5 females; 9 specimens are totally black, Z. Košťál collection.

Tut env., 17 km SW Dorud, 1995 m, 3.6.2009, R. Ambrus leg.; 1 male (totally black with very long antennae), 11 females (1 - totally black, other females with red elytral areas: 1 - black pronotum, 2 - black pronotum with small red spots, 7 - mostly red pronotum) - R. Ambrus collection.

Tootmashour env., 33°24'36"N, 48°54'B, 1995m, 31.5.2010, W. Grosser leg.; 1 male (body length: 16.9 mm), antennae surpassing elytral apices by 3 segments, prothorax black, elytra with 2 big round red spots separated by suture; 1 female (body length: 16.0 mm), antennae

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

reaching elytral middle, pronotum red with black anterior and posterior margins, elytra with 2 big round red spots conjugated at middle; both specimens in W. Grosser collection.

Chaharmahal and Bakhtiari province (Bayer Ahmad-o-Kuhgiluye prov.), 20 km south-eastwards Lordegan, 31°21'17"N, 51°08'48"E, 1940 m, 31.5.2014 W. Grosser; (**Map: loc. 37**), dark population; 32 males (body length: 11.0-18.8 mm), 6 females (body length: 11.4-15.1 mm); both specimens in W. Grosser collection - **Tab. 7** - a pair of this series was designated as paratypes of *P. persicus* Vartanis, 2023; very dark population; male antennae 12-segmented with well-developed 12th segment, can be rather long, from about two time longer than body, surpassing elytral apices by 4 segments, or short, about as long as body; female antennae 11-segmented, reaching elytral middle; pronotum often totally black, or with smaller or wider red spots; about a third of available specimens with totally black elytra; others with small, never conjugated red spots, which may contact at suture.

Material (M.L. Danilevsky collection). 1 male, 1 female, Iran, Esfahan, 40 km SE Aligudars, 35°17'N, 50°05'E, 2254 m, 31.5.-1.6.2009, W.Grosser leg.; 3 males, 2 females, Iran, Hamadan, Baharab, 1600 m, 20.5.2017, K. Hodek leg.

Available photos of *P. wachanrui wachanrui*:

From K. Hodek:

13 males, 8 females - **Tab. 4(2)** - Iran, Esfahan, Chaharmahal, Azizabad, 20 km W Ghahderijan, 32°36'N, 51°7'E, 2170 m, 11.6.2018, K. Hodek leg; 1 female, Iran, North Qazvin, 4 km W Kouhin, 1500 m, 36°22'N, 49°37'E, 31.5.2015, K. Hodek leg; 1 male, Iran, Kordestan, 3.5 km E Dizli, 1350m, 35°22'N, 46°11'E, 25.5.2019, K. Hodek leg; 1 female (dark), Iran, W Azerbaijan, 5 km W Main Bolagh, 2200m, 36°30'N, 46°50'E, 2200 m, 30.5.2017, K. Hodek leg.; 5 males, 5 females, Iran, Kermanshahan - **Tab. 4(1)** - Shamshir env., 1850 m, 34°59'15"N, 46°25'37"E, 6.6.2015, K. Hodek leg.; 16 males, 3 females - **Tab. 2(3)** - Iran, Ardabil 5 km S Deez, 37°16'N, 48°44'E, 1350 m, 5.6.2017, K. Hodek leg.; 3 males, 3 females - **Tab. 5(1)** - Iran, Esfahan, 20 km southwards Shahreza, 31°48'20.6"N, 51°48'50.9"E, 24.5.2017, Dembický leg.

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

Tab. 5. 1-2: *P. w. wachanrui*: 1 - 3 males, 3 females, Iran, Esfahan, 20 km southwards Shahreza, 31°48'20.6"N, 51°48'50.9"E, 24.5.2017, Dembický leg. - K. Hodek collection, photo by K.Hodek; 2 - 8 males, 8 females, same locality, J. Dalihod leg. - R.Ambrus collection, photo K. Ambrus; 3-4 - *P. w. robusticollis*: 3 - 10 males, 4 females, Iran, South Hamadan, Baharab, 34°38'N, 48°10'E, 1600 m, 26.5.2017, K. Hodek leg. - K.Hodek collection, photo by K. Hodek; 4 - 5 males, 6 females, Iran, Lorestan, Razan (18 km NWW Dorud), 1800 m, 33°33'N, 48°53'E, 26.5.2017, K. Hodek leg. - K.Hodek collection, photo by K.Hodek.

Tab. 6. *P. w. robusticollis* - 18 males, 22 females, Iran, Esfahan, 40 km SE Aligudarz, Nowghan env. 2254 m, 1.6.2009, 33°11'35.11"N, 50°04'46.74"E, 1.6.2009, R. Ambrus leg. - R. Ambrus collection, photo by R. Ambrus.

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

From R. Ambrus:

As *P. robusticollis*:

18 males, 22 females (dark specimens dominate), Iran, Esfahan, 40 km SE Aligudars, Nowghan env., 33°11'35.11"N, 50°04'46.74"E, 2254 m, 1.6.2009, R.Ambrus leg.

As *P. wachanrui*:

28 males and 23 females, Turkey, 45 km NEE Adiyaman, Nemrut Dagı, 37°57'51.94"N, 38°44'37.52"E, 14.6.-17.6.2008, R. Ambrus leg.; 1 male, 1 female, Turkey, Adiyaman; 2 males, 2 females, Turkey, Tunceli, 7 km NW Pülümür; 1 male, Turkey, Nemrut ad Tatvan, 38°53'N, 42°19'N; 4 males, 3 females, Turkey, Mus, 8 km SE Solhan, Bulgan Gecidi, 1700-1800 m; 1 male, 3 females, Turkey, Hakkâri, 3 km N of Hakkâri; 8 males, 8 females (half-dark specimens); Iran, Esfahan, 20 km southwards Shahreza, 31°48'20.6"N, 51°48'50.9"E, 24.5.2017, J. Dalihod leg.

From M. Holomčik:

1 male, 1 female, Iran, NW Kermanshahan, 5 km SE Nowdeshah, Vara env., 1200 m, 35.125278°N, 46.296666°E, 22.5.2019, M. Holomčik leg.; 1 male, Iran, West Azerbaijan, 13 km, W Mahabad, Ebrahimeh, 36.7416667°N, 45.5691667°E, 1850 m, 24.5.2019, M. Holomčik leg.; 2 females, Turkey, Kahta, Nemrut Dagı, 2-14.6.1996, P. Jelinek leg.; 1 male, 1 female, Iran, Esfahan, Shahreza, 24-25.5.2009, J. Dalihod leg.; 2 males, Turkey, Kahta env., Nemrut Dagı, 2-14.6.1996, P. Jelinek leg.; 1 male, 1 female, Iran, Esfahan, 40 km SE Aligudars, Nowghan env. 2254 m, 33°11'35.11"N, 50°04'46.74"E, 31.5.-1.6.2009, W. Grosser leg.; 1 male, 1 female, Iran, Ardabil, 41 km SE of Khalkhal, Dasht Tsharom [near Deez], 37.274722°N, 48.748055°E, 1300-1350 m, 27.5.2019, M. Holomčik leg.; 1 male, Iran, Markazi, 28 km N of Saveh, Vardeh env., 35°16'58"N, 50°19'6"E, 1430 m, 20.5.2019, M. Holomčik leg.; 1 male, 1 female, Iran, Hamadan, Baharab, 1650-1850 m, 21.5.2019, M. Holomčik leg.

From Z. Košťál:

16 males, 12 females, Iran, Kordestan, 5 km N of Kamyaran, 34°53'N, 46°58'E, 2100 m, 2.6.2010. Z. Košťál leg.

Available photos of *P. wachanrui robusticollis*

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

From K. Hodek:

10 males, 4 females, Iran, Hamadan, Baharab, 34°38'N, 48°10'E, 1600 m, 26.5.2017, K. Hodek leg.; 5 males, 6 females, Lorestan - Razan (Dorud env.), 1800 m, 33°33'N, 48°53'E, 26.5.2017, K. Hodek leg.

From W. Grosser:

37 males, 11 females, dark population; Iran, Chaharmahal and Bakhtiari province [Bayer Ahmad-o-Kuhgiluyeh prov.], 20 km south-eastwards Lordegan, 31°21'17"N, 51°08'48"E, 1940 m, 31.5.2014, W. Grosser leg.; 1 male, 1 female, Iran, Lorestan, Tootmashour, 33°41'N, 48°90'N, 1995 m, 31.5.2010, W. Grosser leg.; 1 male, 1 female, Iran, Lorestan, Dorud env., 33°27'37"N, 49°05'10"E, 1523 m, J. Romsauer leg.; 2 males, 3 females, Iran, Esfahan, 40 km SE Aligudars, Nowghan env., 33°11'35.11"N, 50°04'46.74"E, 2254 m, 1.6.2009, W. Grosser leg.

From R. Ambrus:

1 male (dark specimen), Iran, Hamadan, Ganjnameh, 34°45'39"N, 48°26'18"E; 1 male (dark specimens), Iran, Lorestan, Horramabad; 3 males (dark specimens), Iran, Fars, 20 km NE Ardakan; 1 male, 11 females (half-dark specimens), Iran, Lorestan, 17km SW Dorud, Tut env., 1995 m, 3.6.2009, R. Ambrus leg.

From Z. Košťál:

7 males, 5 females, Iran, Lorestan between Dorud and Kuh-e-Ostoran mt. 2600-3200 m, 4-6.6.2000, 33°22'N, 49°12'E, M. Kalabza leg.

***Purpuricenus zarudnianus* Semenov, 1903**

Tab. 8

Purpuricenus zarudnianus Semenov, 1903: 358 - Persiae austro-orientalis: terra Geh: alveus Rong [26°13'32"N, 60°12'44"E]; terra Kaserkend: vic. Matasend, inter vic. Tshamp et Surmitsh; terra Bampur: vic. Surmitsh [27°11'42"N, 60°27'17"E]; terra Sarhad: Sadh, Zar, vic Tamin [28°41'40"C, 61°10'B]; curs. super. fl. Rud-i-Ijaadis; Villiers, 1967: 363 - Iran: "Baluchestan, Dachtiari", "Sarbaz"; "Iranshahr", "Kerman", "Djiroft"; Ambrus & Grosser, 2013: 469 - Iran, Kerman prov., 30 km S Sirjan; Ambrus & Tichý, 2017: 101 - Pakistan: Balochistan, Tump (90 km W Turbat [26°6'N, 62°3'E]); Iran: Hormozgan, 5 km SE Khoshangan, 415 m, 27°38,393'N; 56°13,187'E; Kerman, 40 km S Sirjan, 1870 m.

Tab. 8. *P. zarudnianus*: 1 - 47 males, 15 females, Iran, Kerman, 40 km southwards Sirjan, 1870 m, 29°03'35"N, 55°51'41"E, 30.5.2014, W.Grosser leg. - W. Grosser collection, photo by W. Grosser; 2 - 6 males, 3 females with same data, R. Ambrus leg. - R. Ambrus collection, photo by R. Ambrus.

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

Type locality. South-East Iran.

Description. Antennae very long, 11-segmented; male antennae usually more than 2 times longer than body, or shorter to about one third longer than body, female antennae reaching apical elytral forth, always surpassing anterior border of black apical elytral area, or longer, and sometimes surpassing elytral apices; pronotum usually totally red, or sometimes with narrow basal black stripe, or very rare black with big central red spot; elytra black with rather wide red central belt; red elytral are with slightly curved anterior and posterior margins, and very rare narrowed in the middle, sometimes divided by black suture; body length: 11.8-17.0 mm.

Known populations: Iran, Kerman env.; Iran, Kerman, 40 km S Sirjan; Iran, Sistan and Baluchestan, Tamin; Iran, Sistan and Baluchestan, 36 km N Iranshahr; Iran, Sistan and Baluchestan, Geh; Iran, Sistan and Baluchestan, Dashtiari; Pakistan, Tump.

Available photos of *P. zarudnianus*:

47 males (body length: 11.0-19.9 mm), 15 females (body length: 11.8-17.0 mm) - **Tab. 8(1)**, Iran, Kerman, 40km southwards Sirjan, 1870m, 29°03'35"N, 55°51'41"E, 30.5.2014, W.Grosser leg. - W.Grosser collection; 1870 m, 6 males, 3 females - **Tab. 8(2)** - with same data, R. Ambrus leg. - R. Ambrus collection; 1 male, Pakistan, Balochistan, Tump, 90km W Turbat, R. Ambrus leg. - R. Ambrus collection.

Acknowledgement. We are very grateful to the staff of Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Saint Petersburg) and to many friends and colleagues for their photos and valuable information: R. Ambrus (Prague), W. Grosser (Opava), M. Holomčík (Lusatia), M. Lazarev (Moscow), D. Navrátil (Litomyšl), L. Skořepa (Dačice), Z. Košťál (Pardubice).

Map 1.

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

P. wachanrui wachanrui

1 - Turkey, Konya; 2 - Turkey, Nemrut Dagi; 3 - Turkey, Elaziğ; 4 - Turkey, Pulumur; 5 - Turkey, 30 km E Bingol; 6 - Turkey, Buğlan Geçidi; 7 - Turkey, 30 km NW Hakkâri; 8 - Azerbaijan, Nakhichevan, Negram; 9 - Iran, Ardabil, 5 km southwards Deez, 37°16'N, 48°44'E; 10 - Iran, Gilan, Molla Ali River, 36°36'40"N, 49°32'33"E; 11 - Iran, Qazvin, 4km westwards Kouhin, 36°22'N, 49°37'E; 12 - Iran, Qazvin, Alamut, 36°26'41"N, 50°35'10"E; 13 - Iran, Tehran prov., Shemshak, 36°00'56"N, 51°29'10"E; 14 - Iran, Tehran prov., Shemiran, 35°51'3"N, 51°33'6"E; 15a - Iran, North Hamadan, Gardaneh-ye Avadzh, 2500m 35°33'N, 49°10'E; 15b - Iran, Markazi, 28km N of Saveh, Vardeh env.; 16 - Iran, West Azerbaijan, 13km W Mahabad, Ebrahimeh, 36.7416667°N, 45.5691667°E; 17 - Iran, West Azerbaijan, 5 km W Main Bolagh, 36°30'N, 46°50'E; 18 - Iran, Kordestan, Divandareh, Saral, 35°43'46"N 46°52'53"E; 19 - Iran, Kordestan, 3.5km E Dizli 35°22'N, 46°11'E; 20 - Iran, Kermanshahan, Vara; 21 - Iran, Kermanshahan, Shamshir env., 34°59'15"N, 46°25'37"E; 22 - Iran, Esfahan, Varkan, 33°42'56"N, 51°2'57"E; 23 - Iran, Esfahan, Azizabad, 32°36'N, 51°7'E; 24 - Iran, Esfahan; 25 - Iran, Esfahan, 20 km southwards Shahreza, 31°48'20.6"N, 51°48'50.9"E; 26 - Iraq, Penjvin, 35°38'N, 45°56'E; 27a - Iraq, Ravanduz; 27b - Syria, Aleppo.; 28 - Cyprus.

P. wachanrui robusticollis

29a - Iran, Hamadan, Baharab, 34°38'10"N, 48°11'7"E; 29b - Iran, Hamadan, Ganjnameh, 34°45'39"N, 48°26'18"E; 30 - Iran, Lorestan, Khorramabad; 31 - Iran, Lorestan, Zaheh; 32 - Iran, Lorestan, Tootmashour; 33 - Iran, Lorestan, Razan near Dorud; 34 - Iran, Esfahan, 40km SE Aligudarz, Nowghan env. 2254 m, 1.6.2009, 33°11'35.11"N, 50°04'46.74"E, W. Grosser leg.; 35 - Iran, Esfahan, Daran; 36 - Iran, Bayer Ahmad-o-Kuhgiluye prov., 20 km south-eastwards Lordegan, 31°21'17"N, 51°08'48"E; 37 - Iran, Fars, 20 km NE Ardakan, 30°15'34"N, 51°59'07"E.

P. zarudnianus

38 - Iran, Kerman env.; 39 - Iran, Kerman, Sirjan env.; 40 - Iran, Sistan and Baluchestan, Tamin; 41 - Iran, Sistan and Baluchestan,

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

36 km N Iranshahr; 42 - Iran, Sistan and Baluchestan, Geh; 43 - Iran, Sistan and Baluchestan, Dashtiari; 44 - Pakistan, Tump.

REFERENCES

- Adeli E. 1972. Beitrag zur Kenntnis der im Forst schädlichen Insekten des Iran. I. Coleoptera.- Zeitschrift für Angewandte Entomologie. 70(1), 8-14.
- Al-Ali H. A. & Ismail, S.I. 1987. A new species of *Purpuricen* (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Iraq. - Iraqi Journal of Science. 28 (3/4), 536-543.
- Ambrus R. & Grosser W. 2013. Results of the Czech entomological expedition to Iran (2009-2010) (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - Humanity space. International almanac. 2 (3), 461-482.
- Ambrus R. & Tichý T. 2017. New and interesting records of the tribe Purpuricenini J. Thomson, 1861 from China and neighbouring countries (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - Les Cahiers Magellanes (NS). 25: 85-105.
- Aurivillius C. 1912. Cerambycidae: Cerambycinae. Pars 39. - In: Schenkling S. (ed.): Coleopterorum Catalogus. Volumen 22. Cerambycidae I. Berlin: Junk, 108 + 574 pp.
- Danilevsky M.L. 2012. Additions and corrections to the new Catalogue of palaeartic Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) edited by I. Löbl and A. Smetana, 2010. Part. III. - Munis Entomology & Zoology. 7 (1): 109-173.
- Danilevsky M. L. (ed.) 2020. Catalogue of Palaeartic Coleoptera, vol. 6 (1), Chrysomeloidea I (Vesperidae, Disteniidae, Cerambycidae). Revised and updated edition. Leiden / Boston: Brill, i-xxii, 1-712.
- Danilevsky M.L. & Miroshnikov A.I. 1985. Zhuki-drovoseki Kavkaza (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). Opredelitel. Krasnodar: Kubanskiy Selskokhozyaistvennyy Institut, 417 pp., 10 pls. [in Russian]
- Davatchi A., Taghi-Zadeh F. & Safavi M. 1959. Contribution a l'étude biologique et économique des Coléoptères phytophages et xylophages de l'Iran (première note). - Revue de pathologie végétale et d'entomologie agricole de France. 38: 235-252.
- Ganglbauer L. 1882. Bestimmungstabellen der europäischen Coleopteren. VII. Cerambycidae. - Verhandlungen der Kaiserlich-Königlichen Zoologisch-Botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien. 31 [1881], 681-758, pl. 22.
- Heyden L.F.J.D. von, Reitter, E. & Weise, J. 1891. Cerambycidae, pp. 337-355. In Reitter, E. (ed.), Catalogus Coleopterorum Europae, Caucasi et Armeniae rossicae. Berlin: R. Friedländer & Sohn, viii + 420 pp.
- Heyden L.F.J.D. von, Reitter, E. & Weise, J. 1906. Cerambycidae, pp. 499-533. - In: Reitter, E. (ed.), Catalogus Coleopterorum Europae, Caucasi et Armeniae rossicae. Editio secunda. Berlin: R. Friedländer & Sohn, 774 pp.
- Kasatkin D.G. 2021. Notes on the fauna and taxonomy of longicorn-beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of Near East and Transcaucasia. I. - Russian Entomological Journal. 30 (3): 297-304.
- Levrat J.N.G.B. 1858. Description de deux coléoptères nouveaux. - Annales de la Société Linnéenne de Lyon. (2), 5, 261-263.
- Lobanov A.L., Danilevsky M.L. & Murzin S.V. 1982. Sistematicheskiy spisok

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

- usachei (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) fauny SSSR. II. - Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie. 61 (2): 252-277. [in Russian]
- Löbl I. & Smetana A. (ed.) 2010. Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, vol. 6. Chrysomeloidea. Stenstrup, Apollo Books: 924 pp.
- Modarres A.M. 1997. List of agricultural pests and their natural enemies in Iran. Mashhad: Ferdowsi University Press, 429 pp.
- Özdikmen H. 2014. Turkish red list categories of longicorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) Part VI - Subfamily Cerambycinae: Achrysonini, Hesperophanini, Phoracanthini, Cerambycini, Rosaliini, Trachyderini and Callichromatini. - Munis Entomology & Zoology. 9 (2): 609-623.
- Özdikmen H. 2023. Feeding preferences of the turkish members of tribe Purpuricenini J. Thomson with new host plants (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Cerambycinae). - Munis Entomology & Zoology. 18 (1): 187-212.
- Pic M. 1905. Descriptions et Notes Diverses. - Matériaux pour servir à l'étude des Longicornes. 5 (2): 5-15.
- Pic M. 1912a. Notes diverses et diagnoses. - Matériaux pour servir à l'étude des Longicornes. 8 (2): 2-7.
- Pic M. 1912b. Descriptions ou diagnoses et notes diverses (Suite.). - L'Échange, Revue Linnéenne. 28 (329): 33-35.
- Pic M. 1915. Notes diverses et diagnoses. - Matériaux pour servir à l'étude des Longicornes. 9 (2): 4-11.
- Pic M. 1956. Coléoptères du globe (suite). - L'Échange, Revue Linnéenne. 72 (543): 1-4.
- Plavilstshikov N.N. 1940. Fauna SSSR. Nasekomye zhestokrylye. T. XXII. Zhukidrovoseki (ch. 2). Moskva - Leningrad: Izdatel'stvo Akademii Nauk SSSR, 784 + [3] pp. [in Russian]
- Plavilstshikov N. N. 1948. Opredelitel' zhukov-drovosekov Armenii. Izdatel'stvo Akademii Nauk Armianskoi SSR, Erevan, 231 + [1] pp. [in Russian]
- Rejzek M. & Hoskovec M. 1999. Cerambycidae of Nemrud Dagi National Park (Turkey) (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - Biocosme Mésogéen, Nice. 15 [1998]. 4: 257-272.
- Rejzek M., Sama G. & Alziar G. 2001. Host plants of several herb-feeding Cerambycidae mainly from East Mediterranean Region (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - Biocosme Mésogéen, Nice. 17 (2000) (4): 263-294.
- Rejzek M., Sama G., Alziar G. & Sadlo J. 2003. Host plants of longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) from the Balkan Peninsula, Asia Minor, and Iran (Part II). - Biocosme Mésogéen. 19 (2002) (3): 161-162.
- Sama G., Seddighi N. & Talebi A.A. 2008. Preliminary note for a checklist of the Cerambycidae of Iran (Coleoptera - Cerambycidae). - Biocosme Mésogéen, Nice. 25 (3): 101-126.
- Schaufuss L.W. 1871. Neue Purpuricenus-Arten. - Nunquam Otiosus. 1: 209-210.
- Schaum H.R. 1862. Catalogus Coleopterorum Europae. Editio secunda aucta et emendata. Berolini: Friderici Nicolai, 130 pp.
- Semenov A.P. 1907. De tribus novis Purpuriceni formis e fauna Asiae palaearticae (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - Russkoe Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie. 6 [1906]: 254-256.
- Vartanis J. 2023. A new species of the genus Purpuricenus Dejean, 1821 from Iran

M.L. Danilevsky, K. Hodek

- (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - *Munis Entomology & Zoology*. 18 (suppl.): 1803-1808.
- Villiers A. 1967. Contribution à la faune de l'Iran. I: Coléoptères Cerambycidae. - *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France*, (N. S.). 3: 327-379.
- Villiers A. 1979. Coléoptères Cérambycides d'Iran. - *L'Entomologiste*. 35(3): 114-116.
- Winkler A. 1929. Cerambycidae. - In: *Catalogus Coleopterorum regionis palaearticae*. Winkler et Wagner, Wien, pp. 1135-1226.
- Witte E. 1872. *Purpuricen*us Haussknechti, eine neue Bockkäfer-Art. - *Berliner Entomologische Zeitschrift*. 15 (2-3) [1871]: 207-208.

Received: 12.09.2024

Accepted: 28.10.2024